

D4.2: *SILL Tools*

Disclaimer and acknowledgements

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101036388

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Acronym ZeroW **Grant Agreement No** 101036388

Full Title	Systemic Innovations Towards a Zero Food Waste Supply Chain - ZeroW		
Call	H2020-LC-GD-2020 Building a low-carbon, climate resilient future: Research and innovation in support of the European Green Deal.		
Topic	LC-GD-6-1-2020	Type of action	IA
Project coordinator	Inlecom Commercial Pathways		
Project URL	http://www.zerow-project.eu/		
Deliverable	D4.2 SILL Tools		
Document Type	R	Dissemination Level	Public
Lead beneficiary	ILVO		
Responsible author	Lisa Van den Bossche (ILVO)		
Additional authors and contributors	Isabeau COOPMANS (ILVO); Wim HAENTJENS (ILVO);Fleur MARCHAND (ILVO)		
Due date of delivery	30/06/2022	Submission date	30/06/2022

Document information

Document history			
Issue	Date	Comment	Author
V0.1	24.05.2022	Table of content created	ILVO
V0.2	29.05.2022	Toolkit ready, chapter 4 ready	ILVO
V0.3	01.06.2022	Chapters 1, 2 & 3 ready	
V1.0	10.06.2022	First draft of document reviewed	BIOS
V2.0	22.06.2022	Revised document ready	ILVO

Approved by:			
Issue	Date	Name	Organisation
V2.0	28.06.2022	Jovana Vlaskalin	BIOS

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Glossary of terms and acronyms used

[Guidance: Please sort alphabetically]

Table 1 Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Acronym / Term	Description
F2F	Farm-to-Fork
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
SI	Systemic Innovation
SILL	Systemic Innovations Living Labs
SIRL	Systemin Innovation Readiness Level
SWOT	Strengths Weaknesses Opportunities Threats
WP	Work Package
GA	Grant Agreement
LCA	Life Cycly Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LCSA	Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
SKIN	Short Supply Chain Knowledge and Innovation Network
ILVO	Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food
BIOS	BioSense Institute

Executive summary

Systemic Innovation Processes (SIPs) comprise phases of preparation & setup, prototyping, testing, and demonstration & scaling-up. All these crucial phases for solution building require various types of knowledge, infrastructures and skills. With this in mind, each SILL was composed of a network of partners with different expertise's and roles in the food chain. However, making all these partners work together will be demanding in terms of decision making, inclusion of all partners into the solution building, dynamics of co-creation, management, and monitoring of the solution building process. Therefore, the aim of this deliverable is to provide the SILLs with a toolbox comprising various 'tools' that can lever participatory co-creation and include system thinking into the solution building of the SILLs. For every stage of the innovation process SILLs might have different needs, which can relate to (1) identifying and engaging stakeholders, (2) interrogating existing knowledge, (3) creating new knowledge & ideas, (4) thinking ahead & finding solutions to address challenges. In this document, SILLs will find a pre-selected set of tools for every stage and goal.

1. Introduction

ZeroW project summary

ZeroW aims at reducing Food Loss and Waste by employing systemic innovations, to halve by 2030 and to near-zero by 2050. This systemic innovation approach is based on the development of a core demonstrative environment supporting nine Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs) along the value chain, complemented by assessment activities to ensure a long term environmental and economic sustainability of zero-FLW (0FLW) solutions and a just transition towards a near-zero FLW system.

Figure 1 ZeroW at a glance

The ZeroW approach involves the following elements:

Figure 2 ZeroW approach

To reach its goals ZeroW is divided into 11 WPs with different goals, tasks and deliverables. Deliverable 4.2 here presented is strongly linked with deliverable 4.1 Systemic Innovation Maturity Gaps. Deliverable 4.1 aims to provide a systemic tool for monitoring the SILL innovations while deliverable 4.2 provides a set of generic tools that can be used throughout the SILL process to ensure that the issues are approached in a systemic way and that all actors are involved. These tools will mainly be used during the iterations in the Implementation phase and provide a basis for the scaling up (WP6) and Commercialisation (WP7) phases. This integrated approach will increase the uptake of the innovations by the market. The integration of D4.1 and 4.2 into the ZeroW project is visualised in Figure 3.

Figure 3 How D4.1 and D4.2 are interlinked with each other and other work packages

Mapping ZeroW outputs

Purpose of this chapter is to map ZeroW Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the current document.

Table 2 Adherence to ZeroW Grant Agreement deliverable and work description

ZEROW GA Component Title	ZEROW GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D4.2 SILL Toolkit	<i>SILL tools – Will provide participation & systemic thinking tools.</i>	<i>Entire document</i>	<i>SILL Toolkit presents a set of tools with a short description and instructions on how to use them as well as strengths and weaknesses of each tool. There are tools for every step in the innovation process and for different goals.</i>
TASKS			
T4.1 Shared resources for systemic innovation	<i>This Task will develop and manage the systemic innovation resources to be shared with the SILLs, to equip and familiarise/train the SILL members in embedding them in their ideation, prototyping, testing, demonstrating, scaling-up and commercialising activities. There are two groups of outputs for this task and this document reflects the second group, namely the participation & systemic thinking tools. The other group of outputs is presented in D4.1.</i>	<i>Entire document</i>	<i>The toolkit will be presented to the SILLs so they know how to find the right tool. When needed, SILLs can contact ILVO to provide support in applying the more complex tools.</i>

Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The goal of this deliverable is to provide SILLs with a set of tools that stimulate co-creation among the rich network of partners and ensure that the solutions will be developed and evaluated from a systems thinking point of view. Tools are provided for every phase of the innovation process (Preparation & set-up, prototyping, demonstration & commercialisation and scaling up) and for achieving different goals (identifying and engaging stakeholders, interrogating existing knowledge, creating new knowledge & ideas, thinking ahead & finding solutions to address challenges).

In this document we will first outline the theoretical background of how systems thinking and co-creative tools can serve the goal of the SILLs. Next, we will provide practical information on how the toolkit is structured and can be used including how it was developed. Finally, we will briefly present the selected tools.

2. Theoretical background

Food Loss and Waste has become a very complex and wicked problem, there are multiple causes, the causes are hard to identify and there is not one solution. Some solutions even contradict each other or cause other unwanted effects in other parts of the supply chain (Australian Public Service Commission, 2007). For example retailers return products that have less than one-third of the time to their best-before dates remaining to their wholesalers to avoid FLW in their shops thereby causing FLW at the wholesalers (Bhattacharya & Fayezi, 2021).

Solving these kinds of problems requires not only technical solutions implemented by one part of the supply chain but rather a deeper understanding and holistic thinking. Central in ZEROw's approach is the systemic innovation. Knowing that there are different definitions of systemic innovation, Midgley and Lindhult (2017) argue that it is very important to understand and implement systemic innovation as the use of processes that draw upon the idea to support innovators and their stakeholders in systems thinking. Therefore, the discipline of systems thinking is needed as it offers an underlying philosophy which can be very helpful. Systems thinking is based on the belief that the whole is more than a sum of the components. One needs to study and understand the whole and not only the components (Kim, 2000). Understanding how the components interact within a system will bring unique insights and allow one to determine which interventions can really change the system. Furthermore, next to systems thinking, stakeholders have to be brought together in participatory process and concepts like co-creation, multi-actor approach and co-innovation come forward. Co-creation has become a term that is widely used to describe a shift from linear innovation processes towards more participatory processes and co-design (Ind and Coates, 2013). Co-design is the

process of collaboration in which co-creation take place (Koning et al. 2016). However, because co-creation is described in many different practical applications, there is not a fixed framework or plan to follow. We support the suggestion that there is a need for “creating tools for co-creation” (Schrage, 1995; Payne et al., 2007; Roser et al., 2009).

The ZeroW project consists of 11 work packages and 9 SILLs. For the project to reach its goals and create real impact it is paramount that all partners work together and have a shared vision. At the same time each SILL needs to consider which actors will be relevant for developing and commercialising its innovation. Both systems thinking and co-creation will thus be crucial to ensure the uptake by the market. However, both these approaches are rather new in the world of technological innovations and most SILLs do not have experience with these methods. The Sill Toolkit provides a selection of hands-on easy accessible tools that stimulate this way of thinking and acting along the different steps of the innovation development process. The toolkit is integrated in the ZeroW project and will support SILLs in the work they need to do for other work packages. For example, in the preparation phase under WP 9 SILLs are expected to map their stakeholders, the ‘Stakeholder Mapping’ tool can be used to do so. During the three iterative rounds of implementation and the corresponding strategic plans from T 4.2, SILLs will need to make choices on what features to include in their solution. For this, a ‘Multi criterion decision analysis’ or ‘SWOT’ can be helpful. At the same time, these approaches stimulate rich discussions among project partners. When moving on to the scaling up and commercialisation stages in WP 6 and WP 7, SILLs will need to make predictions and involve a broader set of stakeholders. For achieving these goals, tools like ‘Scenario Planning’ and ‘Focus Groups’ can help.

3. Zerow SILL toolkit

3.1 Structure and Methodology of creating the SILL toolkit

The first step in developing this toolkit was understanding the specific needs and requirements of the SILLs in the ZeroW project. An online brainstorm was organised with all WP 4 members and the SILLs. Based on this input and on the Grant Agreement the following needs and requirements were identified:

- developing new technologies
- supporting business environments
- making a swot analysis for the strategic plan
- preparing for LCA, LCC, LCSA and S-LCA
- executing the SILL
- 75% of the tools must be easy to use for users without prior experience

After identifying the needs and requirements, we determined how we could categorize the tools, with the main aim to support users (mainly SILL members) to find the right tool for the right purpose. We defined 3 categorizations. First, the tools were categorized based on what **step of the innovation process** they are most useful for (preparation & setup, prototyping, demonstration or commercialisation & scaling up) as reflected in table 3. A second attribute is the **main objective the tool** can support. We identified the following goals: Map and engage stakeholders, interrogate existing knowledge, create new knowledge, ideas and perspectives, think ahead & find solutions to address challenges/problems, plan & implement/apply knowledge (adapted from Macken-Walsh (2017) and based on experience in multi-actor Horizon 2020 projects like SKIN and AgriDemo-F2F).

Third, **time and effort** to implement and execute the tool is also a relevant attribute, as it can vary between half an hour to a few days or even more.

With this in mind, several sources of online toolkits were scanned to select approximately 20 tools that were considered most suited for the systemic innovation processes running in the ZeroW project. Below you can find an overview of the websites and handbooks that were used to extract tools from.

- <https://odi.org/>
- <http://actioncatalogue.eu/>
- <https://www.mindtools.com>
- <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government>
- <https://www.eawag.ch>
- <https://www.systemsinnovation.io/>
- <https://emergentbydesign.com>
- <https://www.sessionlab.com>
- <https://www.mckinsey.com/>
- <https://sloanreview.mit.edu>
- <https://thesystemsthinker.com>
- <https://www.visual-literacy.org>
- <https://hbr.org>
- <https://www.mindtools.com/>
- Handbook for participatory action research, planning and evaluation
- www.systemsinnovation.io
- <http://kstoolkit.org>
- <https://www.systemicdesigntoolkit.org/>
- <https://www.contify.com/>

For each selected tool, a fact sheet was made, presenting a brief summary of the tool along with the identification of its main strengths and weaknesses and a reference to a source where more information can be found. The fact sheets are presented in the annex of this document. Further elaboration on the toolkit, its

purpose and proposed usage, will be introduced to the SILLs during the ZeroW face-to-face meeting on 12-13th July 2022. During the ZeroW project, the SILLs can contact ILVO for support in preparing the application of a tool for addressing a challenge they are faced with. ILVO will however not act as a moderator or facilitator. Nevertheless, based on future needs, we are available for some (2-4) dedicated trainings during the ZeroW project on the use of these tools during general meetings or an online webinar.

The development of the toolkit is a continuous and bi-directional process. Based on the feedback from the SILLs, tools can be added if they feel certain goals cannot be met with the selected tools. SILLs that have used a tool and noticed unclarities or they made certain adaptations are invited to provide this feedback so that we can adapt and optimise the content of each tool along the ZeroW project.

3.2 How to use the Sill toolkit

3.2.1. Choose the tool

The SILL toolkit will be integrated in the ZEROW website where the tools are organised based on the goal of the stakeholder involvement and the stage of the process of innovation. Colours will indicate how much time is needed to use the tool and peppers will indicate the effort needed to prepare the tool. Partners and SILLs will also be able to consult the toolkit via the ZEROW Teams folder. The excel file in annex 2 provides an overview of all 20 selected tools with an indication on their main goal for stakeholder involvement and their relevance in the different stages of the innovation process, plus their time and effort needed. SILLs that are searching for a tool can choose to browse the website or the SILL Tools Overview to find a tool that matches their needs.

Stage in the Innovation process

Tools can be searched by stage of the innovation process as reflected in table 3. We identified the following four stages to be most relevant for the SILLs (adapted from European Commission, 2014):

- *Preparation & setup*: This stage involves identifying the exact FLW issue that you want to solve, mapping it and understanding the issue at hand as well as it's connection to the broader system. Based on that analysis a conceptual solution is developed.
- *Prototyping*: During prototyping the conceptual solution is translated into a first test in a controlled environment, a prototype.
- *Demonstration*: Learnings from the prototype building are the basis for further developing the solution into marketable end product or service. This

usually happens through multiple iterations of demonstration, adapting and testing in (semi-)controlled environments.

- *Commercialisation & scale-up*: only after the final product or service is ready and tested in an uncontrolled environment, it can be brought to the market at a larger scale. Now the focus is on reducing the production costs by optimising the processes and increasing quantities.

Most tools are useful in more than one step of the innovation process and we encourage SILLs to use the same tool multiple times to gain experience with the tools. Furthermore, a colour coding was used to indicate whether the tool is a co-creation and collaboration tool (green) or rather a tool to stimulate systems thinking (blue).

Table 3 SILL tools categorised per stage in the Innovation process, green for co-creation and blue for system thinking tools

Tool	Stage in the Innovation process			
	Preparation & Setup	Prototyping	Demonstration	Commercialisation & Scale-up
Brain storm	X	X		X
Tomorrow headlines	X			
Visualisation tools	X	X	X	X
Focus Group	X	X		X
SWOT	X	X	X	X
Scenario Planning	X		X	X
Fish bowl	X	X	X	X
Sabotage		X		
Multi Criteria Decision Analysis		X		X
Systemic Innovation Readiness		X	X	
Theory of systems change		X	X	X
Collaboration Model		X	X	X
Problem tree analysis			X	X
Actor mapping	X			X
Competitor Mapping				X
Force Field analysis	X		X	
Causal Loop Diagram	X	X	X	X
Systems mapping	X	X		X
Future Scenarios	X	X		
Iceberg	X	X		

Main goal of stakeholder involvement

SILLs will often encounter specific challenges or issues for which they want solutions. The tools can also be browsed by goal as reflected in table 4. Macken-Walsh (2017) defined **five goals of engagement** of stakeholders. Based on the experience of multi-actor Horizon 2020 projects (like SKIN and AgriDemo-F2F), The description of these goals was adapted slightly to fit more with ZEROW SILLs purposes.

- *Map and engage stakeholders*: Identifying all stakeholders that are relevant for your solution and understanding their role is best done in an early stage but can be repeated later on as the project evolves. From this mapping it is important to decide which stakeholders to engage with and on what level. Many tools have the engagement of stakeholders not as their main objective but as welcome side effect.
- *Interrogate existing knowledge*: The SILLs are composed of very complementing and experienced partners. Extracting the knowledge that exists in the team or with a broader set of stakeholders is an important goal to develop a workable FLW innovation.
- *Create new knowledge, ideas and perspectives*: Combining existing knowledge in a new way and looking at the same issue from different perspectives to gain new insights.
- *Think ahead & find solutions to address challenges/problems*: During the entire innovation process there will be challenges arising and different choices to make on how to tackle these challenges. Additionally some of these tools stimulate foresight so that you can anticipate certain issues rather than solve them after they presented themselves.
- *Plan & implement/apply knowledge*: Translating good ideas and new knowledge into actionable plans will be needed at the end of each iterative round of demonstration and testing as well as in the commercialisation and scale-up phase.

Again most tools can be used to serve different goals and Table 4 on page 16 focuses on the main goal of a certain tool. SILLs are encouraged to use and adapt the tools if needed to match better with their goal. This feedback will be incorporated into the toolkit. Here as well, a colour coding was used to indicate whether the tool is focussing on participation (green) or on systems thinking (blue).

Time and effort

For every tool, time and effort needed to execute the tool is indicated in Table 5 on page 17. Preparation time and time needed for analysis of the results is not

included. The effort needed for each tool is expressed with a level 1, 2 or 3 (in the fact sheets this is indicated with 1, 2 or 3 peppers). About 75% of the tools can be used by someone without prior knowledge based on the fact sheets (levels 1 or 2), only three tools have three peppers and require some practice or support of a facilitator (Theory of Systems Change, Causal Loop Diagram, Systems mapping).

Table 4 SILL tools categorised per main goal, green for co-creation and blue for system thinking tools

Tool	Main Goal				
	Map & engage stakeholders/ actors	Interrogate Existing Knowledge	Create new knowledge & ideas	Think ahead & find solutions to address challenges /problems	Plan & implement/ apply knowledge
Brain storm			x	x	
Tomorrow headlines	x		x		
Visualisation tools		x	x		
Focus Group	x	x			
SWOT		x		x	
Scenario Planning		x		x	x
Fish bowl				x	x
Sabotage	x	x			
Multi Criteria Decision Analysis	x				x
Systemic Innovation Readiness		x	x	x	
Theory of systems change					x
Collaboration Model					x
Problem tree analysis				x	x
Actor mapping	x			x	
Competitor Mapping			x	x	
Force Field analysis		x		x	
Causal Loop Diagram		x	x	x	
Systems mapping	x	x		x	
Future Scenarios	x		x		x
Iceberg		x			

Table 5 SILL tools categorised by Time & Effort required, green for co-creation and blue for system thinking tools

Tool	Time & Effort	
	Time	Effort
Brain storm	1 -2 hrs	1
Tomorrow headlines	1 -2 hrs	1
Visualisation tools	1 -2 hrs	1
Focus Group	3 - 4 hrs	2
SWOT	1 -2 hrs	2
Scenario Planning	3 - 4 hrs	1
Fish bowl	1 -2 hrs	1
Sabotage	1 -2 hrs	1
Multi Criteria Decision Analysis	1 -2 hrs	2
Systemic Innovation Readiness	3 - 4 hrs	2
Theory of systems change	3 - 4 hrs	3
Collaboration Model	1 - 2 hrs	2
Problem tree analysis	1 - 2 hrs	2
Actor mapping	3 - 4 hrs	2
Competitor Mapping	1 - 2 hrs	1
Force Field analysis	3 - 4 hrs	2
Causal Loop Diagram	3 - 4 hrs	3
Systems mapping	3 - 4 hrs	3
Future Scenarios	1 - 2 hrs	2
Iceberg	1 - 2 hrs	2

3.2.2. Apply the tool

After choosing a tool, reading carefully the fact sheet will give the information needed to apply the tool. In addition, further information can be accessed mostly through the provided link on the fact sheet, and for some tools a template can be downloaded through the same link. The possibility of using a template is clearly mentioned on the fact sheet. In all other cases, the references are only mentioned for interested readers and respecting intellectual property. In some cases it will be recommended to first use another tool from the toolkit to prepare for a more advanced tool, this is clearly mentioned in the fact sheets. As mentioned before, during the ZeroW project, the SILL members can contact ILVO for support in preparing the implementation of the tool.

3.2.3. Provide feedback

After using the tool or when users do not find a suitable tool after browsing the toolbox, it is important to provide this feedback to ILVO. Unclearities or recommended adaptations to tools or fact sheets will improve the toolbox along the ZeroW project. When the toolbox does not offer a tool that is fit for purpose, ILVO can assist users in finding a new tool. When relevant, the newly selected tools will be added to the toolbox.

The use of the toolbox will be monitored during the ZeroW project: SILLs will document each time they use a tool (in what kind of meeting, for what purpose, who participated, etc.). This feedback will be collected periodically via the SILL progress and mid-term reports under WP 4. This fits into task 4.2, managing the SILL shared resources and interfacing with the toolkit developers for upgrades the SILLs might require during the project.

Most tools are useful in multiple stages and serve different goals. We encourage the SILLs to re-use certain tools in every iteration of the SILL process, this will allow to map progress and evolution.

4. Zerow Tools – Short Overview

Brainstorm

Basic participatory tool to generate new ideas and find solutions to problems. By doing this in a group you create a shared vision.

Tomorrows' headlines

Brainstorming technique that combines individual thinking and group thinking. The goal is to stimulate foresight and be prepared for different possible outcomes.

Actor Mapping

Basic systems thinking tool that requires you to map all potentially relevant actors and their position in your project.

Focus Group

A focus group is a technique for gathering qualitative data through a group interview. The aim is to generate a rich understanding of the participants knowledge, beliefs and experiences.

Problem Tree Analysis

Visualisation technique that helps to fully understand a problem. By doing this in a group you create a shared understanding of the problem at hand.

Iceberg Model

Tool to better understand an existing situation. Stimulates a group to look beyond the observable facts to underlying patterns, structures and mental models.

Future Scenarios

Planning tool that uses envisioning technique that stimulates foresight and helps you prepare for different scenario's. For groups of 10-12 people.

Scenario Planning

Strategic tool that stimulates foresight and helps prepare for different possible outcomes by identifying critical uncertainties and understanding their potential impact.

Systems Mapping

Systems thinking tool that visually represents the system you are working in with nodes and connection between nodes. Can be complemented with causal loop diagrams.

Competitor Mapping

Strategic business tool that stimulates you to look outside your own company boundaries and compare yourself with other companies on a number of different dimensions

Causal Loop Diagram

System dynamic tool to identify and map structures in a system by mapping feedback loops. Identifying this structure will help to understand the behaviour that follows.

Multi Criteria Decision Analysis

Decision making tool that allows comparing different options on multiple criteria.

Visualization Techniques

Make a visual representation of an idea, process or structure. Some tools stimulate convergent thinking, others divergent thinking.

Force Field Analysis

Systems thinking tool that helps to identify and better understand the driving forces and blocking factors in developing a change process.

SWOT

Strategic tool that provides insight in a projects' internal and external characteristics. Often used for long term strategic decisions and for identifying blind spots.

Sabotage

Co-creation tool to identify blind spots in your project plan by taking the perspective of a saboteur. Creates strong internal support for the final project plan.

Systemic Innovation Readiness Level Assessment

Tool for monitoring a Systemic Innovation Process in a participatory way. Perfect for preparing scaling up of systemic solutions to complex problems. First, the tool stimulates the inclusion of as many relevant innovation dimensions as possible, which helps reaching systemic innovation. Second, the tool guides the assessment of readiness levels in the different innovation dimensions, which helps identifying obstacles to and strategies for scaling up.

Fish Bowl

Discussion facilitation tool. Combines an inner circle of experts and an outer circle of observers. Combines detailed discussion in a small group with involving and informing a larger group.

Theory of Systems Change

Systems thinking tool that aims to identify the preconditions that are needed to reach the desired change by breaking up the process into different time frames and determining the preconditions for change in each step.

Collaboration Model

Strategic business tool that stimulates you to look outside your own company boundaries and compare yourself with other companies on a number of different dimensions.

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6. Annex I: ZeroW Toolkit

BRAINSTORM

WHAT	<p>Basic participatory tool to generate new ideas and find solutions to problems. By doing this in a group you create a shared vision.</p>
WHEN TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Stage(s): Preparation & setup, prototyping, commercialisation & scale-up ■ Goal: Engage stakeholders, Interrogate existing knowlegde, create new knowledge & ideas, think ahead & find solutions to address challenges/problems ■ Type: Participation & co-creation tool ■ Time & Effort: 1 - 2 hrs
HOW TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Appoint a facilitator before the brainstorm. ■ Online: use tools like MIRO or Lucid spark. Offline: provide pens and post-its. Make sure everyone can see all ideas. ■ Compose the group (5 to 7 participants) and make sure it is diverse ■ Define the problem you want to solve & stress that there are no bad ideas, feasibility is not important ■ Give people time to generate as much ideas as possible on their own ■ Ask everyone to share their ideas ■ Start a group discussion on the ideas but don't follow one train of thought for too long ■ Only at the end: evaluate the ideas

BRAINSTORM

STRENGTHS	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Fun and informal method to gather a lot of new perspectives■ Increases support for the solution because everyone contributed■ You can leverage the full creativity potential of the group by building on each other's ideas■ Brainstorming can be complemented with lot's of techniques for specific situations
WEAKNESSES	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Challenging to involve all participants also more introverted■ Be carefull not to stifle creative ideas that seem unrealistic■ Brainstorming in group means you can't follow your own train of thought and this might block your ideas

Source: Mind Tools Brainstorming - Creativity Techniques from MindTools.com

TOMORROWS' HEADLINES

WHAT	<p>Brainstorming technique that combines individual thinking and group thinking. The goal is to stimulate foresight and be prepared for different possible outcomes.</p>
WHEN TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Stage(s): Preparation & setup■ Goal: Map & engage stakeholders/actors, create new knowledge & ideas, think ahead & find solutions to address challenges/problems■ Type: Participation & co-creation tool■ Time & Effort: 1 - 2 hrs
HOW TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Brainstorming tool that uses envisioning technique.■ Ask participants to close their eyes and envision the moment in which the product or service will be launched.■ Participants write fictional News paper articles, blog posts or ted talks about that moment.■ Ask questions like how will it be introduced to its potential users? what features will be highlighted?■ Stimulate provocative and creative writing.■ Like in a brainstorm, there are no bad ideas or articles - everyone writes his own article.■ Share your articles or ted talks with the group and look for common ground. What impact does this have on your project?

TOMORROW'S HEADLINES

STRENGTHS	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Helps to align on a common vision with the project team■ Working backwards helps to get a new perspective■ Fun and informal method to gather a lot of new perspectives■ Participants can follow their own train of thoughts when writing■ Brainstorming technique that involves the more introverted as well
WEAKNESSES	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Ensure enough time for the group discussion afterwards■ Important to find common grounds in the different stories■ Powerfull technique for a very specific question

Source: Tomorrow's Narratives | Service Design Tools & Headlines from the Future SessionLab

VISUALISATION TECHNIQUES

WHAT	<p>Make a visual representation of an idea, process or structure. Some tools stimulate convergent thinking, others divergent thinking.</p>
WHEN TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Stage(s): Can be used in any stage■ Goal: Interrogate existing knowlegde, create new knowledge & ideas■ Type: Participation & co-creation tool■ Time & Effort: 1-2 hrs
HOW TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Mind Map: Structures ideas in a way that provides overview and detail, stimulates divergent thinking■ Venn diagram: Draw partially overlapping circles, write similarities in the overlapping parts and what is unique in the parts belonging to one circle. Illustrates differences, similarities and relations. Provides an overview and Stimulates convergent thinking■ Tree diagram: Draw a tree, the roots represent the inputs and the leaves the outputs. Match roots and leaves to reflect the hierachy or consequences of decisions. Stimulates convergent thinking■ 2by2 matrix: Categorizes a system by two simple variables resulting in four clusters. Stimulates divergent thinking■ Life cycle diagram: Maps a process into phases (introduction, growth, maturity an decline). Stimulates convergent thinking and gives overview.

VISUALISATION TECHNIQUES

STRENGTHS

- Can be done alone or in group.
- Helps to clarify complex issues.
- Different visualisations possible so you can adapt this to your situation.
- Making a visual representation forces you to clear out ambiguity and come to the essence of an issue.

WEAKNESSES

- Important to choose the right visualisation technique for the right purpose.
- Not a goal in itself but a way to understand a process or system.
- These tools are for you to explore ideas, systems or processes. They are not necessarily suited to communicate your ideas to others!

References:

A Periodic Table of Visualization Methods (visual-literacy.org)
Visualizations That Really Work (hbr.org)
Visual Reminders – MSP Guide

FOCUS GROUP

WHAT	<p>A focus group is a technique for gathering qualitative data through a group interview. The aim is to generate a rich understanding of the participants knowledge, beliefs and experiences.</p>
WHEN TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Stage(s): Preparation & setup, prototyping, commercialisation & scale-up■ Goal: Engage stakeholders & interrogate existing knowledge■ Type: Participation & co-creation tool■ Time & Effort: 3 - 4 hrs
HOW TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Focus on a specific topic: identify the the problem/research question and the stakeholders that can provide insight to answer it.■ Group participants in groups of 8-10 people■ Create an environment in which people feel free to talk openly, some people may need to be encouraged■ Ask qualitative, open-ended questions (why? what? how?) or combine with a problem tree, scenario planning or iceberg tool to stimulate the group discussion.■ There needs to be a facilitator to keep the group focused on the topic at hand■ Summarize the discussion in a written report. Analyse the answers but also non-verbal communication and group dynamics

FOCUS GROUP

STRENGTHS	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Interactive environment and better flow of ideas than in individual interviews.■ This method can produce deeper insights on the participants' attitudes, ideas and preferences than other methods as it allows for direct observation of the participants' immediate reactions as well as more in-depth discussions on the research topic.
WEAKNESSES	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Due to the small number of participants, the results are not representative for the target group.■ The individual characteristics of the participants can present challenges for the moderator/facilitator.
Source: ActionCatalogue - method	

SWOT

WHAT	<p>Strategic tool that provides insight in a projects' internal and external characteristics. Often used for long term strategic decisions and for identifying blind spots.</p>
WHEN TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Stage(s): Can be used in any stage ■ Goal: Interrogate existing knowlegde, create new knowledge & ideas ■ Type: Participation & co-creation tool ■ Time & Effort: 1 - 2 hrs
HOW TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ A SWOT is a strategic tool that identifies: ■ Strengts are internal aspects that are going well. ■ Weaknesses are internal aspects going not so well ■ Opportunities can be internal or external and help to overcome weaknesses building on strengts ■ Threats can also be internal or external factors that inhibit change ■ You can make one SWOT or split up the group and make several SWOTS that you discuss together ■ Guide the discussion with the following questions: How can we use our strengths to valorise our opportunities? How can we use our strengths to neutralise threats? How can we deal with our weaknesses? What about the long term threats? ■ End with Defining action points

SWOT

STRENGTHS	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Stimulates participants to all share their input.■ Participative way of strating a constructive learning process.■ Stimulates joint actions.■ Can be used at different levels of analysis.
WEAKNESSES	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ There is a risk of missing one or more important threats.■ It is not a one time exercise but should be repeated in different stages - it is a process more than a tool.■ It is a starting point for discussion but does deliver a competitive strategy an output.
<p style="text-align: right;">References:</p> <p>SWOT Analysis – MSP Guide What's swot in strategic analysis? - Pickton - 1998 - Strategic Change - Wiley Online Library</p>	

SCENARIO PLANNING

WHAT	<p>Strategic tool that stimulates foresight and helps prepare for different possible outcomes by identifying critical uncertainties and understanding their potential impact.</p>
WHEN TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Stage(s): Preparation & setup, demonstration, commercialisation & scale-up■ Goal: Interrogate existing knowlegde, create new knowledge & ideas, plan & implement/apply knowledge■ Type: participation and co-creation tool■ Time & Effort : 3 - 4 hrs if actor mapping and driving forces are available it can go faster.
HOW TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Strategic tool in which four scenarios for the future are identified & analysed.■ Step 1: Identify the issue at hand and explore it. Ideally you have allready done an actor mapping.■ Step 2: Identify the driving forces, if available use the results of the driving forces tool.■ Step 3: Narrow down to 2 driving forces. Be very critical that these are the correct ones. These will be called the two critical uncertainties.■ Step 4: Map the two critical uncertainties in a 2 by 2 matrix so that you end up with 4 scenarios. For each scenario ask what happens and which interventions are needed. Write a story of +/- 500 words for each scenario.■ Step 5: Reflect on each scenario, discuss the implications on your innovation.■ The result is a shared framework for strategic thinking

SCENARIO PLANNING

STRENGTHS

- Stimulates foresight by envisioning a range of different future scenarios.
- Considers both internal and external factors.
- Considers the joint impact of different uncertain elements.
- Helps to make decisions under uncertainty.
- Can be used as a tool to evaluate investment proposals.

WEAKNESSES

- Success depends on participants ability to overcome cognitive biases:
 - availability bias:** Focusing on what you already know.
 - Probability neglect:** over estimation of unlikely events
 - Stability bias:** assuming that the future will be like the past
 - Over-confidence:** tendency to choose only those scenarios you deem most likely
 - Social biases** that stifle a free and open debate

References:

Scenario Planning – MSP Guide
Overcoming obstacles to effective scenario planning | McKinsey
Scenario Planning: A Tool for Strategic Thinking (mit.edu)

FISH BOWL

WHAT	<p>Discussion facilitation tool. Combines an inner circle of experts and an outer circle of observers. Combines detailed discussion in a small group with involving and informing a larger group.</p>
WHEN TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Stage(s): Demonstration, commercialisation & scale-up■ Goal: Think ahead & find solutions to address challenges/problems, apply knowledge■ Type: Participation & co-creation tool■ Time & Effort: 1 - 2 hrs
HOW TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Use this tool to discuss a hot topic with the entire group in a dynamic way. Groups can range from 6 to 30 people.■ Introduce the topic and methodology to the group.■ Make a small circle with 6- 8 chairs and a second larger circle around the small one with the remaining chairs.■ A group of experts on the topic at hand take a seat in the inner circle and leave one chair open. The experts discuss the topic and the outer circle (observers) listen and observe in silence. They note down questions or remarks.■ Observers can move in and sit on the open chair if they want to contribute. They should rotate regularly.■ After +/- 1 hour discussion finish with a 30 min debrief where everyone can speak freely. Provide a document with key learnings.

FISH BOWL

STRENGTHS	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Allows an in depth expert discussion in a larger group setting.■ Brings transparency in the discussion at hand.■ Increases trust and understanding on complex issues.■ Stimulates a dynamic conversation.
WEAKNESSES	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ The experts must be open to discuss the topic in an open way and aim to make it understandable for the entire group.■ The observers must remain silent, if they want to contribute a lot it might mean that they are not listening to the inner circle any more.
<p>Source Fish Bowl – MSP Guide Knowledge Sharing Tools and Methods Toolkit - Fish Bowl (kstoolkit.org) Fishbowl Discussion - YouTube</p>	

SABOTAGE

STRENGTHS	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Stimulates divergent thinking: 'what did we miss?'■ Identifies all possible doubts and fears people did not feel like expressing.■ Identifies established patterns that you were not aware of but could have an impact on your project.■ Makes people laugh together.
WEAKNESSES	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Some people might not feel comfortable 'sabotaging' their own plan or fear that this is not loyal to the team.■ Previously raised concerns that have not been addressed can pop up again. This can be the time to find new solutions to known issues. But do try to focus on obstacles that are not yet on your radar!
<p>References:</p> <p>11f418_c56ab3b5fc5c455091178ac894ab359d.pdf (wix.com) (go to Handbook for Participatory Action Research, Planning and Evaluation Better Evaluation - page 100)</p> <p>Chevalier, Jacques M. and Buckles, Daniel J. (2003) Handbook for participatory action research, planning and evaluation. SAS2 Dialogue, Ottawa.</p>	

SABOTAGE

WHAT	<p>Co-creation tool to identify blind spots in your project plan by taking the perspective of a saboteur. Creates strong internal support for the final project plan.</p>
WHEN TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Stage(s): Prototyping stage■ Goal: Map & engage stakeholders/actors, interrogate existing knowlegde■ Type: Participation & co-creation tool■ Time & Effort: 1 - 2 hrs
HOW TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Explain the prototype plan to your project team and ask them to write on a post-it one or two things that would make the plan fail. These can be internal or external events.■ Stimulate creative ideas and ensure people that they are not committed to their sabbotage ideas.■ Categorize all the ideas into clusters as you see relevant.■ Distinguish between ideas that would be a nuisance and ideas that really make the plan fail.■ Next try to turn every sabbotage idea into a success factor. What could you do to make sure the idea cannot fail the plan? How can you make your plan stronger?■ You can do this in pairs, try to work on someone else's sabbotage ideas. You can also do this in group. Do not ask who wrote done which idea to stimulate free flow of thoughts.

MULTI CRITERIA DECISION ANALYSIS

WHAT	Decision making tool that allows comparing different options on multiple criteria.
WHEN TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Stage(s): Can be used in any stage■ Goal: Interrogate existing knowlegde, create new knowledge & ideas■ Type: participation & co-creation tool■ Time & Effort: 1 - 2 hrs
HOW TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Technique to assist in choosing between different options. You can use online tools or an excel sheet.■ Step 1: Identify the different options (columns).■ Step 2: Determine the criteria by which to evaluate all options (rows).■ Step 3: Score every option on all criteria. Make sure you are consistent by comparing scores per criterium.■ Step 4: Determine the value/weight of each criterium (first row)■ Step 5: Multiply the scores from step 3 and step 4 to obtain weighted scores, add them up to obtain one score per option.■ Look at the outcomes and assess if a small difference in weights would alter the outcome? can you combine certain options or even make new options? Don't simply take the winning outcome for granted but use this tool to understand the pro's and con's of different options.

MULTI CRITERIA DECISION ANALYSIS

STRENGTHS	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Stimulates coherent decision making.■ Makes the criteria to judge on explicit.■ Flexible tool, the criteria used are different for each situation.■ The criteria are best determined in group, the assessment and weight attribution can be done individually and added up later or in group - depending on group dynamics.
WEAKNESSES	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Participants can score with the end result in mind instead of with an open mind.■ Important to make the reasons behind the reasons for a high or low score explicit to understand the decision making process. The same goes for the weights assigned to each criterion.
<p>References:</p> <p>ActionCatalogue - http://actioncatalogue.eu/method/7393 https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/7612/1132618.pdf available on teams A Short Story about Multiple Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) - YouTube</p>	

SYSTEMIC INNOVATION READINESS

WHAT	<p>Tool for monitoring a Systemic Innovation Process in a participatory way. Perfect for preparing scaling up of systemic solutions to complex problems. First, the tool stimulates the inclusion of as many relevant innovation dimensions as possible, which helps reaching systemic innovation. Second, the tool guides the assessment of readiness levels in the different innovation dimensions, which helps identifying obstacles to and strategies for scaling up.</p>
WHEN TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Stage(s): Prototyping, demonstration ■ Goal: Interrogate existing knowlegde, create new knowledge & ideas, think ahead & find solutions to address challenges/problem. ■ Type: Systems thinking tool ■ Time & Effort: 3 - 4 hrs
HOW TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Describe the problem you want to solve and the innovation you propose as a solution ■ Determine which dimensions are relevant for your innovation - ask the question 'could this be an issue for scaling?' ■ Make a <u>Radar or spider graph</u> with as many axes as you have identified dimensions and a 10 point scale. ■ Determine the current readiness level for each selected dimension on a scale from 0-9 ■ We recommend to use a focus group to determine the curent level and include outside experts. You need to corroborate your scores! ■ Only when the previous level has fully been reached you can tick of that level ■ Repeat the proces after x months

SYSTEMIC INNOVATION READINESS

STRENGTHS	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Provides an all encompassing approach to evaluate your innovation's potential.■ Adaptable to your needs to keep it time efficient.■ Stimulates interaction within the project group and with outside experts.■ Strong visualisation tool.
WEAKNESSES	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Risk of leaving out a dimension that later on turns out to be crucial.■ Requires a lot of knowlegde in different domains.■ Requires the use of other tools like focus groups to bring all the knowledgte together.■ Important to have the right actors involved (suggestion: make an actor map).
<p>Inspired by: Bruno, I., Donarelli, A., Marchetti, V., Panni, A. S., Covino, B. V., Lobo, G., & Molinari, F. (2020). Technology readiness revisited: A proposal for extending the scope of impact assessment of European public services. ACM International Conference Proceeding Series, 369–380. https://doi.org/10.1145/3428502.3428552 Sartas, M., Schut, M., Proietti, C., Thiele, G., & Leeuwis, C. (2020). Scaling Readiness: Science and practice of an approach to enhance impact of research for development. Agricultural Systems, 183(August), 102874. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2020.102874</p>	

THEORY OF SYSTEM CHANGE

WHAT	<p>Systems thinking tool that aims to identify the preconditions that are needed to reach the desired change by breaking up the process into different time frames and determining the preconditions for change in each step.</p>
WHEN TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Stage(s): Demonstration, commercialisation & Scale-up■ Goal: Plan & implement/apply knowledge■ Type: Systems thinking tool■ Time & effort: 3 - 4 hrs
HOW TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Use this tool to build a collective theory of change. Causal loops and system maps are valuable inputs. Make a team of 2 tot 3 participants that are part of the core team.■ Start with agreeing on the timeframe of the exercise and draw a timeline. Then define the strategic final impact that the project wants to reach.■ We use iterative loops of backwards thinking, 'what preconditions are needed for these outcomes?'■ When you reach the middle reverse the order and start from the present forward. What are the inputs to the system? try to split them up per dimension of innovation readiness.■ During the process you might need to make assumptions or encounter strategic risks, list these in separate boxes below.■ The final model is tested by reading it from the beginning until the end.

THEORY OF SYSTEM CHANGE

STRENGTHS	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ As a next step you can identify for each intermediate outcome indicators for success.■ The process can be repeated until you get a simple and concise narrative.■ Aligns team members on a complex plan for change.
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WEAKNESSES	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Biases will impact the project planning, make sure to note down all assumptions so that these are known and understood.■ Not suited for large teams, but you can do iterations with different team compositions.
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Source:
systemicdesign toolkit.org - [available on teams](#)

COLLABORATION MODEL

WHAT	<p>The collaboration model helps you to clarify your projects' what, why and how. It is an excellent preparation for the Business Model Canvas.</p>
WHEN TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Stage(s): all stages■ Goal: Plan & implement/apply knowledge■ Type: Systems thinking tool■ Time & Effort: 1 - 2 hrs
HOW TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Use the template via the download link in the sources below.■ Centrally you have the Organisation's DNA, this is your vision. Next define your purpose, why are you doing this?■ In step 3 define the capacities you need, identify roles, skills and competencies and mention who will take what roles. Are there roles missing?■ In step 4 and 5 identify what you will do and how it will be done.■ In step 6 describe the value impact that the project is expected to create.■ In step 7 and 8 list the preconditions that are needed to make the project possible and estimate the resources and costs. How will the project be financed?■ In the final step define the criteria you will use to evaluate the success of the project.

COLLABORATION MODEL

STRENGTHS	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Socially creative tool.■ Can serve a first draft of the business model.■ Works best when used with the entire working group that already has a shared vision, if there are new members they will need more preparation time.■ Offers a model to discuss the team purpose.
WEAKNESSES	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Is only suited for a small core team.■ It works well if the team has shared values, if this is not the case this needs to be dealt with first.■ It is only the first step towards a business model.
<p>Source: systemicdesign toolkit.org - available on teams</p>	

PROBLEM TREE ANALYSIS

WHAT	<p>Visualisation technique that helps to fully understand a problem. By doing this in a group you create a shared understanding of the problem at hand.</p>
WHEN TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Stage(s): Preparation & setup, demonstration■ Goal: Think ahead & find solutions to address challenges/problems, plan & implement/apply knowledge■ Type: Systems thinking tool, participation and co-creation tool■ Time & Effort : 1 - 2 hrs
HOW TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Works best in groups of 6-8 people, make sure everyone can see the flip-over on which you draw a tree.■ Step 1: identify the issue, all participants need to see this as a pressing issue they are willing to work on. Write this in the trunk of the tree.■ Step 2: write down the causes of the issue on post-its and put them in the roots of the tree■ Step 3: write down the effects of the issue on post-its and put them in the branches of the tree■ Arrange the post-its in a cause and effect logic■ The goal is to generate a usefull discussion on the topics. provide time and space to capture all causes and effects.■ Once the tree is finished, debate the different causes and effects. which ones are most impactfull? can be resolved quickly? how are they evolving over time?

PROBLEM TREE ANALYSIS

STRENGTHS	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Provides a shared framework for understanding an issue.■ Differentiate between the problem and its causes.■ Breaks down a complex problem in manageable chunks while maintaining an overview.■ Identify connections between causes and effects, leading to possible win-win scenarios .
WEAKNESSES	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Essential to have a good representation of different stakeholders in the group.■ Depending on the group it might be challenging for participants to share their ideas - in that case a facilitator is advised.■ Something can be a cause and effect at the same time, in that case make two post-its with the same item.
<p style="text-align: center;">References:</p> <p>Problem Tree – MSP Guide D8_1_Problem_Tree_Analysis.pdf (eawag.ch) Planning tools: https://odi.org/en/publications/planning-tools-problem-tree-analysis/ Step 1: Identifying the focal issue with 'Problem Tree Analysis' technique - YouTube</p>	

ACTOR MAPPING

WHAT	Basic systems thinking tool that requires you to map all potentially relevant actors and their position in your project.
WHEN TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Stage(s): Preparation & setup, commercialisation & scale-up■ Goal: Map & engage stakeholders/actors, Think ahead & find solutions to address challenges/problems■ Type: Systems thinking tool■ Time & Effort: 2 - 4 hrs
HOW TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Create a list of stakeholders who form part of the system.■ Determine relations between actors.■ Get to know the actors, what are their values, incentives, models and power.■ Determine relevance of actors: direct, indirect or system.■ Determine the influence or power of the actors.■ Determine which actors are aligned and which ones are opposed.■ Map them in quadrants based on their influence and alignment. You can use the template or make your own.■ Observe from the perspective of the actors involved.

ACTOR MAPPING

STRENGTHS	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Allows you to identify opportunities for alliances and detect potential conflicts.■ Useful to identify gaps.■ Helps to understand how adoption might take place.■ Understanding actors allows you to speak their language and thus optimize your communication.
WEAKNESSES	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ When aiming to change complex systems, typically many actors are involved making the exercise time intensive.■ Actors are not necessarily involved themselves, so assumptions are made on their values and incentives.
<p>Sources</p> <p>Actor mapping Canvas available on teams</p> <p>Find the template on teams</p>	

COMPETITOR MAPPING

WHAT

Strategic business tool that stimulates you to look outside your own company boundaries and compare yourself with other companies on a number of different dimensions

WHEN TO USE

- **Stage(s):** Commercialisation & scale-up
- **Goal:** Create new knowledge and ideas
- **Type:** Systems thinking tool
- **Time & Effort:** 1 - 2 hrs

HOW TO USE

- Decide on what dimensions you want to compare. There are numerous possible dimensions and subdimensions.
- Some examples: product features, target customers, pricing, marketing strategy, strengths, weaknesses, competitive advantage, customer reviews, quality, delivery service, after sales support, location, customer loyalty,..
- Make sure that you can in fact obtain data for every dimension that you choose. Some possible sources are: competitors newsletters, stores, social media platforms, products, trade journals, conferences, customer surveys.
- Make a matrix in which you list own company and your competitors and score them on each dimension.
- For dimensions that are not quantifiable make sure to leave room for open discussion - this will generate valuable input.

COMPETITOR MAPPING

STRENGTHS

- Helps you to understand you market segment
- Gives a holistic overview of you position in the market and allows details if you zoom in on product features for example
- Allows you to spot large differences with you competitors wich will give a clear view on your competitive strengths and weaknesses
- Helps to spot opportunities in the market

WEAKNESSES

- Requires thorough preparation: gathering information on your competitors on the dimensions under comparison.
- You can only compare on dimensions that you have information on. You generally don't know the cost effectiveness of you competitors for example.

References:

https://www.mindtools.com/pages/article/newSTR_60.htm
<https://www.contify.com/resources/blog/competitive-matrix/>

FORCE FIELD ANALYSIS

WHAT	<p>Systems thinking tool that helps to identify and better understand the driving forces and blocking factors in developing a change process.</p>
WHEN TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Stage(s): Preparation & setup, demonstration■ Goal: Interrogate existing knowlegde, create new knowledge & ideas■ Type: Systems thinking tool■ Time & Effort: 3 - 4 hrs
HOW TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Tool that supports structured decision making.■ Take a flip-over and in the middle of it note down the desired change to discuss.■ Brainstorm in the group and note down on the left hand side all forces that would block the change from happening - these can be internal or external.■ Do the same for all forces that would support the change, note them on the right hand side.■ Score each force (1-5) and add up totals for and against.■ Use this as a starting point to discuss how to overcome blocking factors and strenghten driving forces.■ Works best in groups of 6-8 people, make sure everyone can see the flip-over

FORCE FIELD ANALYSIS

STRENGTHS

- Helps you understand the driving forces at play when implementing change.
- Attempts to quantify the current driving forces involved in a change process.
- Great starting point to understand a current situation and possible ways forward.
- A Swot analysis can be a great starting point.

WEAKNESSES

- Don't use this tool when you need absolute certainty.
- For important decisions, we recommend to use a combination of tools.
- Don't focus on the numeric outcome but leave enough time for rich discussion to take place.

References:

Force Field Analysis – MSP Guide
Force Field Analysis - Decision-Making Skills from MindTools.com
Force Field Analysis - YouTube

CAUSAL LOOP DIAGRAMS

WHAT	<p>System dynamic tool to identify and map structures in a system by mapping feedback loops. Identifying this structure will help to understand the behaviour that follows.</p>
WHEN TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Stage(s): Can be used in any stage■ Goal: Interrogate existing knowledge, create new knowledge, think ahead & find solutions to address challenges■ Type: Systems thinking tool■ Time & Effort: 3 - 4 hrs
HOW TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Determine the system/theme you want to map and the boundaries you will respect. Identify the variables in your system and the links between them, they can evolve in the same (S or +) or opposing (O or -) direction.■ Reinforcing loops compound change in one direction with even more change eg one nasty comment leads to nasty resposns and a conflict arises.■ Balancing loops try to bring a system to a desired state and keep it here eg eating when hungry and stopping when you have had enough■ Both type of loops can be combined in one system and there can be a shift in dominance between the two loops.■ When mapped over time: reinforcing loops go up, balancing loops are cyclycal until plateau is reached.■ Delays in the loop cause the resulting behaviour to come with a delay - very hard to predict the outcome in such a system

CAUSAL LOOP DIAGRAMS

STRENGTHS

- Offers a high level view of a system, first step in system dynamics.
- Can be expressed in behaviour over time graphs which offer a different way of looking at the same process.
- Forces you to clearly select a theme, time horizon, boundaries and aggregation level.
- Allows you to think about delays in the system.

WEAKNESSES

- No distinction between stock variables and flow variables and thus the diagrams offer less detail than stock & flow diagrams.
- It helps determine the leverage points but not necessarily the direction in which to manipulate them to obtain the desired result.

Source:
The Systems Thinker – Video: Introduction to Causal Loops - The Systems Thinker

SYSTEMS MAPPING

WHAT	<p>Systems thinking tool that visually represents the system you are working in with nodes and connection between nodes. Can be complemented with causal loop diagrams.</p>
WHEN TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Stage(s): Preparation & setup, prototyping, demonstration, commercialisation & scale-up ■ Goal: Map & engage stakeholders/actors, interrogate existing knowledge, think ahead & find solutions to address challenges/problems ■ Type: Systems thinking tool ■ Time & Effort: 3 - 4 hrs
HOW TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Pre-work: actor map & identify stages of the process under study. ■ Brainstorm on key forces and patterns in the system. These can be social, economic, technological, environmental and are represented as nodes. Use different colour for different stages or actors. ■ Determine the variables of every node, what is changing? ■ Determine links between nodes and what is exchanged between them. Money, goods, information? Do nodes influence each other in a positive or negative way? ■ Identify key nodes based on their connectedness. ■ Framing: determine what the boundaries are of the system you want to zoom in on. ■ Are there delays? feedback loops?

SYSTEMS MAPPING

STRENGTHS	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Modular tool that you can build upon gradually.■ Helps to think dynamically and understand the system.■ Powerfull visualisation tool.■ Allows to build a shared vision of the system, its challenges and opportunities.
WEAKNESSES	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Requires some knowlegde on the concepts used.■ Experience with the tool is recommended.■ It is challenging to identify the correct links and relations between the nodes, some relations are indirect.
<p>Source: Systems Mapping (systemsinnovation.network) available on teams Systems Mapping - YouTube</p>	

FUTURE SCENARIOS

WHAT	<p>Planning tool that uses envisioning technique that stimulates foresight and helps you prepare for different scenario's. For groups of 10-12 people.</p>
WHEN TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Stage(s): Preparation & setup, prototyping■ Goal: Map & engage stakeholders/actors, create new knowledge & ideas, think ahead & find solutions to address challenges/problems plan & implement/apply knowledge■ Type: Participation & co-creation tool■ Time & Effort: 1 - 2 hrs
HOW TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Describe the project and how you measure the success of your project. What are the success factors?■ Split up in two groups. each group imagines a different future: the best case and worst case scenario. Avoid extreme thinking and stay realistic.■ Each group describes the scenario based on the success factors and identifies the trends that support this version of the future - use a flip chart■ Bring the groups together and compare both versions of the future. use this as a starting point to describe the Likely future Scenario.■ Use the worst case scenario to identify possible threats and the the best case scenario to identify opportunities■ Determine what threats and opportunities are most important to focus on

FUTURE SCENARIO'S

STRENGTHS	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Clarifying the future helps to identify the necessary actions to reach that future.■ Helps to determine our impact in creating the future.■ Does not require much time.■ Seeing the future helps to plan it 'if we can see it, we can built it.
WEAKNESSES	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Predicting the future is impossible, the tool only gives a possible version of the future.■ Based on the input of participants and not on actual data,so it is prone to participants' biases■ Beware not to come up with extemely unlikely scenario's

Source: 3 Tools for Futures Thinking & Foresight Development | emergent by design

ICEBERG MODEL

WHAT	<p>Tool to better understand an existing situation. Stimulates a group to look beyond the observable facts to underlying patterns, structures and mental models.</p>
WHEN TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Stage(s): Preparation & setup , prototyping■ Goal: interrogating existing knowledge■ Type: systems thinking■ Time & Effort: 1 - 2 hrs
HOW TO USE	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Draw an iceberg on a flip chart. The thip of the iceberg (10%) represents the observable events. The remaining 90% is under water and invisible.■ The first layer below the surface represents patterns, things that evolve over time, trends we observe.■ The second layer represents the structure that sustains the trends and legitimate the causes.■ The bottom layer are the Mental Models that drive our behaviour and typically maintain the existing structure or lead to change.■ Try to identify the different layers of the iceberg in group. The goal is to see that the visible events are caused by underlying patterns, structures and models.

ICEBERG MODEL

STRENGTHS	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Triggers deeper analysis and reflection on observed events.■ Allows changing the root causes instead of the symptoms.■ Can be done in large or small groups.
WEAKNESSES	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Not easy to apply to more complex issues with many different mental models.■ Does not offer an action plan or to do list as outcome of the exercise.
<p>Source: Iceberg Model Explained (systemsinnovation.io) available on teams Iceberg model - YouTube</p>	

7. Annex II: SILL Tools Overview

Tool	Stage				Main Goal					Time & Effort		Type	
	Preparation & Setup	Prototyping	Demonstration	Commercialisation & Scale-up	Map & engage stakeholders/actors	Interrogating Existing Knowledge	Create new knowledge & ideas	Think ahead & find solutions to address challenges/problems	Plan & implement/apply knowledge	Time	Effort	Participation & co-creation	Systems thinking
Brain storm	x	x		x			x	x		1h-2hrs	1	X	
Tomorrow headlines	x				x		x			1h-2hrs	1	X	
Visualisation tools techniques	x	x	x	x		x	x			1h-2hrs	1	X	
Focus Group	x	x		x	x	x				3-4hrs	2	X	
SWOT	x	x	x	x		x		x		1-2 hrs	2	X	
Scenario Planning	x		x	x		x		x	x	3-4hrs	1	X	
Fish bowl	x	x	x	x				x	x	1 -2 hrs	1	X	
Sabotage		x			x	x				1h-2hrs	1	X	
Multi Criteria Decision Analysis		x		x	x				x	1-2 hrs	2	X	
Systemic Innovation Readiness		x	x			x	x	x		3-4 hrs	2		X
Theory of systems change		x	x	x					x	3-4hrs	3		X
Collaboration Model		x	x	x					x	1hrs-2hrs	2		X
Problem tree analysis			x	x				x	x	1hrs-2hrs	2		X
Actor mapping	x			x	x			x		3-4hrs	2		X
Force Field analysis	x		x			x		x		3-4hrs	2		X
Causal Loop Diagram	x	x	x	x		x	x	x		3-4hrs	3		X
Systems mapping	x	x		x	x	x		x		3-4hrs	3		X
Future Scenarios	x	x			x		x		x	1 -2 hrs	2		X
Iceberg	x	x				x				1 -2 hrs	2		X